

Representing the circular economy research landscape - a text analysis approach based on context specific noun phrase embeddings

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Introduction

The concept of a circular economy (CE), which can be described by maintaining the value of resources with the help of eco design as well as sharing, repairing, recycling, refurbishing and reusing of products, is a key topic of interest in the 21st century, since it supports the shift towards a more sustainable future (Bocken et al., 2019). Therefore, knowing about the state-of-the-art research and keeping track of the newest innovations with respect to CE is significant for various (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). This study attempts to answer the following research question:

How can the research landscape of CE be described by means of quantitative analysis and what are continuous research streams in CE?

We define a research landscape as consisting of different scientific knowledge fields evolving over time in research streams. A scientific knowledge field on the other hand is the union of scientific knowledge elements that can be approximated by information embedded in scientific articles (Zhang et al., 2020).

Based on these definitions we follow an approach that uses noun phrases appearing in scientific articles as proxies for scientific knowledge elements and identify the research landscape upon dynamic clustering of those noun phrases.

Methodology

The methodology can be separated in the three parts of data collection, data processing via text mining and clustering, and deep dive based evaluation (see Figure 1). We collected 9,616 scientific publications between 2010 and 2021 from the Dimensions database (Hook et al., 2018).¹ The collected data for each publication contains the abstract, publication year and affiliations. Our search string² is adopted from previous literature reviews on circular economy (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). We analysed the publication dynamic to destine the three time frames for the later part of the methodology, where the evolution over time should be tracked.

¹ Here, we used a tool called *Knowledge Analytics for Technology and Innovation*, developed and hosted by the Fraunhofer Institute for Technological Trend Analysis INT.

Figure 1. Research Model. Representing the CE research landscape and identifying research streams.

In the next part, the abstracts are used for the further analysis, since they contain the condensed information embedded in scientific articles that we consider as the key element for representing the research landscape. To prepare the data for a clustering approach, the SciBERT model from BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) was used with the purpose of retrieving vector embeddings for each word.

The SciBERT model is a pretrained BERT model specifically prepared for analyzing scientific data (Beltagy et al., 2019). BERT has the advantage of getting context-dependent and sentence specific word embeddings against other approaches like word2vec. In parallel, the python module Spacy was used to extract the noun phrases appearing in the abstracts. These noun phrases are the smallest measurable entity of scientific information in the publications, here representing scientific knowledge elements. Combining the noun phrases with the retrieved vector embeddings of the words inside each noun phrase, a sentence specific quantified representation of each noun phrase was created. This step addresses two popular problems of word embeddings, which are the phrase semantics as well as the order of words. Subsequently, a data cleaning

² ("circular economy") AND (year:%2021% OR year:%2020% OR year:%2019% OR year:%2018% OR year:%2017% OR year:%2016% OR year:%2015% OR year:%2014% OR year:%2013% OR year:%2012% OR year:%2011% OR year:%2010%) AND has_text:%true%

process that included lemmatization as well as the removal of stopwords was carried out with help of the R package `textstem`.

As preparation for clustering and evaluation, the data was split in the beforementioned three time frames to allow a detailed analysis over time. For each of these time frames, identical noun phrases with a similar (based on cosine distance) vector representation were combined into a noun phrase representation to avoid ambiguity. The summarized noun phrases of the different time frames were then one after another clustered using the `k means++` algorithm on the noun phrase embeddings. The decision for `k means++` was made based on it being one of the most used and best performing clustering algorithms (Bahmani et al., 2012). The result of this clustering process were multiple clusters for each of the time frames that represented the scientific knowledge fields occurring in the CE research at the given time slot. Lastly, the most representative noun phrases of each cluster were chosen based on a time frame specific TF-IDF representation. With these terms it was possible to describe the content of a cluster and represent the research landscape over the different clusters. With the purpose of tracking the evolution of the landscape over time, the forward oriented intersections between all clusters from the different time frames were measured. This means, that for each cluster of a specific time frame all noun phrases were collected and then individually compared with all clusters from the consecutive time frame in order to detect similarities. The number of noun phrases appearing in two consecutive clusters of different time frames described the intersection size which is divided by the number of noun phrases in the cluster from the previous layer. In that regard, a high intersection percentage indicated that a specific scientific knowledge field was researched in a continuous research stream.

Results

The methodology results in 12 clusters for the years 2010 to 2017 revolving around 276 unique noun phrases. The second time frame consists of 15 clusters containing 1,462 unique noun phrases for 2018 and 2019 and the third time frame dissolves into 18 clusters including 2,813 unique noun phrases for the years 2020 and 2021. In Figure 2 the evolution of the clusters size is visualized. Calculating the intersection between consecutive time frames we identify 58 cluster intersections using a threshold of at least ten percent of the noun phrases reappearing in the next cluster. The manual analysis of these intersections leads to eight continuous research streams. The topics of the research streams can be clearly distinguished from each other with the help of the TF-IDF keywords. The range of topics addressed in the research streams includes innovation management, waste management, climate change and ghg emissions,

digitalization, supply chains, construction industry, CE principles, risk management and more. One example for a research stream are the two clusters (or scientific knowledge fields) from the first time frame about climate change as well as human and social health that over time converge into one scientific knowledge field in the last time frame, dealing with mixed topics of both clusters like the carbon footprint or social justice.

Discussion and Conclusion

Our research enables different actors such as researchers, managers and policy makers to track and understand the evolution of the field CE. The found topics and scientific knowledge fields also align with previous researches like the literature review from (Chauhan et al., 2022) about digitalization and CE in which similar thematic foci are described. Our method complements the existing research with this very unique and specific approach based on the combination of noun phrase extraction and sentence specific word embeddings which also yields a lot of potential that still needs to be further refined like e.g. finding emerging topics, new knowledge elements, trends or top contributors of specific research fields in CE research.

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